

CHANGES – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society

SPOKE 6 – History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage

Deliverable 3

Technical–scientific report of the database for measurement, archiving, management and analysis of data in support of restoration and conservation strategies

Deliverable information

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Spoke information

Spoke 6 develops integrated methodologies for the historical understanding, conservation and restoration of cultural heritage, promoting a multidisciplinary approach involving humanistic, archaeological, scientific and technological research. It supports sustainable and participatory planning, emphasising the active involvement of citizens to increase awareness and shared responsibility in heritage protection. Addresses the challenges of historic cities and landscapes, including preventive maintenance and enhancement of historic values. It combines scientific and humanistic skills to manage and analyse complex data, creating a virtuous circle between historical analysis and conservation interventions.

It promotes cultural participation as a factor of social cohesion and sustainability, analysing case studies of risk, conservation and valorisation, from landscape monuments to mobile artefacts, from Palaeolithic to modern times. Museums, archives, parks and archaeological sites are ideal places to implement shared strategies, guaranteeing communities the right to enjoy cultural heritage.

Spoke partners

Spoke 6 is coordinated by the University of Catania, with Pietro Maria Militello as Spoke Leader, and by the Istituto Centrale del Restauro, with Giorgio Sobrà as Spoke Co-Leader. The implementation of the Spoke's activities is supported by a qualified network of affiliated institutions, namely Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna (UniBO), Fondazione 1563 (F1563), Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD), Università degli Studi di Milano (UniMI), Università degli Studi di Torino (UniTO), Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa (UniSOB), and Università Federico II di Napoli (UniNA). Through their complementary scientific, technical, and institutional competences, these partners contribute to the achievement of the Spoke's research, innovation, and knowledge-transfer objectives within the broader framework of the CHANGES programme.

Executive summary

Among to the aims of the spoke, one of the target of the project is the creation of a platforms for the collection, management and interpretation of data for the conservation and restoration of cultural heritage.

To achieve this purpose it is necessary to carry out a survey of existing platforms and databases, not only strictly connected with the topic, but also taking as examples models and software that deal with the processing of other types of data.

For instance, will be taken into consideration databases linked to archeology and monumental heritage.

First of all, it is necessary to start from the analysis and the existence or otherwise of databases or platforms dedicated to restoration.

This first survey investigated the platforms that can be consulted online, while it will be necessary to continue with more specific investigations for the internal databases of restoration institutions, with the caution of the presence of sensitive data in relation to privacy and certain economic situations.

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1. Introduction

One of the challenges of our project was to combine the study and analysis of the history of the restoration and conservation of works of art with the data derived from scientific analyses and the constitutive study of materials and the actual restoration processes. Another challenge is to investigate the topic of preservation and restoration in different contexts, from the close-up of individual artefacts to the broader context of archaeological and architectural contexts.

In this first phase it is important to check how the data is entered both on a qualitative and quantitative level, what types of data are put in the platform, how they are analyzed and described, whether synthetic or analytical informations, whether they take into consideration aspects related to diagnostics and whether they coincide with the files of the artworks created by the ICCD (Istituto centrale per il catalogo e la documentazione) by the Ministry of Culture, therefore if they are in line with ministerial parameters.

2. Data summary

To facilitate and make the analysis more effective, a table has been created, from which the data was extracted and will be presented here in a broader description for each individual case analyzed.

The table has been divided into the following areas: institution, description, software, analytical description of artworks, type of technology used, year, financing entities, online, open access.

In this report, first of all, will be taken into consideration databases dedicated to the restoration of artworks and secondly platforms used for other data that could serve as a model for the creation of a new platform. In this first phase it is important describes in detail the software used and its characteristics because it could be useful to know the features and positive or negative aspects of data storage.

The first database analyzed was the **RES.I** (<https://archiviosistorico restauratori.it/>) created by Giovanni Secco Suardo Association from the Archivio Storico Nazionale dei Restauratori Italiani (ASRI). Born in 1995, ASRI has seen, since its inception, the participation of the Ministry of Culture, through the Central Institute of Restoration, as a promoting and supporting body alongside the Giovanni Secco Suardo Association, which manages and coordinates the various activities.

The project addresses, through an interdisciplinary approach, on the one hand the needs of rescue, collection, conservation and use of important documentary materials at risk of dispersion, acquiring private archives of Italian restorers and other protagonists of Italian restoration, and on the other it promotes a constant activity of studies and research on the history of restoration throughout the national territory. The results of these study activities are inserted into the RES.I database. (Italian Restorers) which then allows cross-research on the conservation histories of works of art, on techniques, on materials, on the events of the restorers.

The RES.I database area includes investigations into sources bibliographic and archival (also using the results of the ASRI area) aimed at reconstructing the biographical profiles of Italian restorers and their restoration interventions, through a specially designed relational and multimedia database, which also manages the information relating to the works and sources used.

It represents an advanced research tool on the history of restoration in Italy: nourished "container" of critical information on Italian restorers and their interventions. It's about a specially designed relational and multimedia

database, which also manages information relating to the works and sources used.

The management of information through RES.I, without limiting study methods and paths even very much different, allows data and research results to be shared and integrated at a national level, and allows more effective access to the information filed, suggesting connections and investigations transversal, otherwise unthinkable, allowing us to reconstruct and relate the complex professional events of the restorers, their interventions, as well as the conservative history of the works of art.

The information assets of the RE.S.I Database prove to be very large, extremely precious, not

only on the scientific level in support of historical research, but on the level of the current operations of restorers and the central and decentralized bodies of the MiC, as they are an indispensable source for the planning of new restoration interventions.

The new web application of the RES.I Database has been online since 2022, after the over 20,000 forms concerning Restorer, Intervention, Work, Document, Other profiles, Artists, Institutions/companies were subjected to formal reclamation in compliance with the compilation rules.

At the same time, the web application using the application architecture, called JAMStack, which allows for excellent performance exploration and research of contents, while maintaining a clear separation with the corresponding editorial environment (i.e. CMS) dedicated to filers.

One of the main features of the new RES.I web application is public exposure of the JSON/REST APIs that allow to programmatically query the entire database of RES.I. All JSON/REST APIs are documented online via swagger, making it easier significantly the integration of RES.I contents from any external application.

This feature was designed from the beginning with the intention of making the contents of RES.I

easily integrated with the General Catalog of Cultural Heritage.

The new web application offers two defined orthogonal ways of consulting the contents exploration and research respectively. Exploration, primarily oriented towards scholars, uses a tabular representation of the contents, which can be sorted and filtered by column, to then show the details of the individual cards. Research, geared towards a broader audience, uses the service instead full text search by Algolia, appropriately fed with the contents of the most relevant fields of the cards.

The aspects of access management, data validation and publication, coordination and training

of the researchers are managed by the Giovanni Secco Suardo Association, with technological support of the SINAPSI software house for the necessary IT updates and developments.

The RES.I database online and open access from 2022 is organized through five main tabs: Restorer, Intervention, Work, Document, Other profiles, Artists, Institutions and companies, Archives.

The Restorer sheet collects the data and biographical information, the list of interventions implemented and documented, the abbreviated citation of all the sources used to compile the

form. It is composed of a registry part with formalized data also relating to some aspects of the activity (topography, chronology, areas of specialization), a free text part intended for narration of the biographical story and a portion of sources cited according to normalized criteria.

The Intervention Sheet catalogs the various restoration interventions implemented and documented and specifies their details various operations, with a description of the procedures.

When completing this form, reference is made, whenever possible, first to each single restoration report consulted or any other archival document of this nature, from where technical-descriptive information can be obtained. This data is then integrated by information obtained from bibliographic sources.

The Other profiles tab is dedicated to other important figures involved in the intervention restoration (superintendents, art historians, restoration technicians, etc.) collects data and news biographies, the list of documented interventions and the abbreviated citation of all the sources used for filling out the form. It is composed of a registry part with related formalized data also some aspects of the activity (topography, chronology, areas of specialization...), a text part free intended for the narration of the biographical story and a part of sources cited according to criteria normalized.

The Artwork sheet contains the essential elements necessary for identifying the work and the list of restoration interventions carried out. It is not a historical-critical catalog of the works, but a database to support the history of the restoration, the Opera files have a value auxiliary, only as a reference tool for the Intervention sheets.

The Document tab includes the extended registration of all sources, not only textual but also it had to be in the project plan relating to multimedia documents (images, films, sound recordings, ...) mentioned in the sheets Restorer and in the Intervention tabs. This link is not online and open access.

About Jamstack: it is an architectural approach that decouples the web experience layer from data and business logic, improving flexibility, scalability, performance, and maintainability.

It enables a composable architecture for the web where custom logic and 3rd party services are consumed through APIs.

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Despite the premises and care of the data, the information contained in the database RES.I is not exhaustive, the description is too brief and don't match with the ICCD standard.

This is certainly a first approach to online cataloging information on restorations deduced from archives, which allows you to easily move between who carried out the restoration intervention, when and where the restoration reports are kept.

The interface is simple, well-conceived and easy to use, but however the text inserted on the restorations is not very exhaustive on diagnostic investigations and interventions, it also lacks attached photographic documentation.

The dataset is made up of entities that are quantitative rather than qualitative, even if the number of sheets entered is only a part of those that could be inserted.

The database of **SISCA (Società italiana di Storia della critica d'arte)** is not easy to find online because it is an item in the menu website dedicated to restorations.

The SISCA has decided to resume one of the objectives that the Central Institute of Restoration had proposed in the documents of its origin in 1939, that is, to establish a sort of centralized national archive of all restorations carried out by the Italian Superintendencies. The project aims to create a digital archive of the most significant restoration interventions by geographical area, which also collects the documentation of the main restoration interventions carried out in Italy over a period of time that from the present day goes as far back as possible into the last century. In this page it is possible to insert one or more restoration cards, also accompanying them with any images or documents, and consult the cards inserted so far with the possibility of searching within them.

The user can independently send a sheet filling a form, which will then be approved by SISCA, or doing a free search in the dataset. The dataset is online and open access, generated by wpDataTables. This software is a WordPress table plugin which makes work with tables, charts and data management.

Create Tables and Charts in WordPress in three basic steps: Provide table data (Upload your file, paste a MySQL query, provide a URL, or just input the data manually); Configure if you want

(Fine-tune your table - if you want it to be responsive, editable, have conditional formatting, etc.); Publish in a post or page (Once you're satisfied with the table, insert it in a post or page using standard WP Editor or Visual Composer).

It is possible to search in the database through: Typology; Subject / Title; Author(s); Dating; Material; Technique; Measurements (cm); Location; City /

Region; Provenance; Restorer(s); Date of restoration; Restoration intervention; File; Card inserted by.

Despite this scheme attached files are not included, but it is similar with the aspect of ICCD standard.

It is possible download the entire database in pdf or in Excel file.

At the moment 140 cards have been inserted relating to those produced by the Sicilian Superintendence (but only focus on architecture, decorative arts, sculpture of Palermo and Monreale).

The information is quite exhaustive on the state of the objects before and after the restoration intervention, however the data relating to the description are synthetic, although referring to the diagnostic investigations with precision.

Regarding the ongoing digitization activity of the Restoration and Photographic Fund by the **Opificio of the Pietre dure in Florence (OPD)**, thanks to PNRR Stream 5 "Digitization of restoration archives" MIC3 – Investment 1.1 "Strategies and digital platforms for cultural heritage" Sub- investment 1.1.5 – Digitalisation", at the moment it is only possible to describe the software used. First OPD uses CDS-ISIS and SiCaR software, now the open source software Archimista.

Archimista is an open-source application for the description of historical archives and the creation of inventories, censuses and guides aimed at operators and archival institutes. The need to create Archimista is due to the overcoming of the previous regional software, Sesamo and Guarini, now obsolete, and the need to move towards a new idea of description more open to the world of the web. The application was born from a collaboration agreement signed in 2010 between the Lombardy Region, the Piedmont Region and the General Directorate for Archives. In the initial phases, coordination was guaranteed by the University of Pavia. Since 2012 the coordinating body has been the Polytechnic of Milan. The works reached the release of version 2.0.0 in November 2015.

The peculiarity that distinguishes Archimista from other software is its web-based nature, a characteristic with a strong impact on the organization of filing activities and on the workflow: the work can be shared by multiple operators at every stage and not just once the product is finished. The perspective in which Archimista places itself is also decidedly that of the elaboration of archival descriptions intended, in addition to the production of printed tools such as inventories and guides, for use on the Internet within information systems.

Archimista also stands out from the experience of Guarini and Sesamo for the presence of digital objects, which can be associated with any level of the archival complexes, with the archival units, with the producers, with the conservators and with the sources.

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It allows the creation of archival description databases according to international (ISAD, ISAAR) and national (NIERA) standards, the description according to national standards and related vocabularies of photographs, drawings and prints, the generation of reports, in pdf and rtf formats, inventories, censuses and guides for publication online or on paper.

Archimista is released in two versions: a stand alone version for individual work in the absence of a network and a server version for work on remote locations which allows simultaneous intervention by multiple operators. Functions and plots of the two versions are identical: data can therefore be exported from one to the other.

Archimista is free software: you may redistribute or modify it under the terms of the GNU General Public License as published by the Free Software Foundation.

The Central Institute for Archives has published version 3.1.1 of the ArchiMista archival inventory software on Github, a platform for the publication and collaborative development of open source software.

As part of an institutional agreement with the Lombardy Region and the Archival and Bibliographic Superintendence of Lombardy, ICAR has undertaken some corrective, adaptive and evolutionary maintenance activities on the open source Archimista software to encourage its use in the State Archives and Archival and bibliographic superintendencies.

In particular, following specific evolutionary maintenance activities, version 3.1.1 of Archimista is fully interoperable with the SIAS and SIUSA national archive systems and with the SAN Research Tools Portal, thanks to the implementation of compliant import and export functions to the ICAR interoperability paths in XML format (ICAR-Import path, which integrates, for the respective entities envisaged by the ArchiMista data model, coding schemes in EAD3, EAC-CPF and SCONS2 format). These functions are in addition to those already existing which provide the possibility of exporting data in the CAT-SAN and METS-SAN formats provided by the SAN - National Archive System.

In the ArchiMista 3.1.1 version, a Virtual Machine was also made available, which can be used both in a Windows environment and in Mac-OS systems. This Virtual Machine can be installed on your local systems by offline emulating the functionality and performance of the server version and can therefore be adopted in place of the standalone version of the software.

The ISCR, Central Higher Institute of Restoration in Rome, on its website has a dedicated section where the user can choose between completed restorations, ongoing restorations, historical restorations.

The online open access sheets (<http://www.icr.beniculturali.it/pagina.cfm?usz=5>) are simple web pages with various items: Presentation, historical-critical analysis, execution techniques,

state of conservation and previous interventions, restoration intervention, bibliography, clients and partners.

The data entered are analytical and allow a fairly accurate description of the diagnostic investigations and interventions conducted.

The **ICPAL, Istituto centrale per la patologia degli archivi e del libro**, is an agency of the Ministry of Culture, dependent on the General Directorate of Education and Research, with the aim of protecting and restoring books, archive documents and other paper and parchment artefacts, as well as photographic, cinematographic and digital materials.

The historical archive of the ICPAL preserves documentation relating to the history and activity of the Institute in the period from its establishment in 1938 until approximately 1975, when it passed to dependent on the Ministry for Cultural and Cultural Heritage.

The collection of the historical archive is currently the subject of cataloging and inventory work which will allow its physical consultation at the Institute and will then include digitization and online consultation.

The section of the historical restoration archive is currently involved in the PNRR Stream 5 project "Digitization of restoration archives". The collection is inventoried and catalogued, available for online consultation via the following link: <https://archimista-icpal.cultura.eu.ngrok.io/>

ArchiVista was born from an agreement between the Lombardy Region and the Polytechnic of Milan, ArchiVista 3.1.1 is developed by INGLOBA360 s.r.l., ArchiVista is released under the GPL open source license with the aim of encouraging its development and growth.

ArchiVista is created in compliance with archival standards, SAN and NIERA parameters.

It allows the publication of archival databases produced with Archimista (or converted into Archimista) including digital objects.

In the section dedicated to the archive of ICPAL, there is a detailed description of the archival history and the archival consistency (1773 archival units). The Fund preserves the files with the files, correspondence, minutes and other documentation that testify to the restoration activity carried out.

The open access allows to search independently among the various archive files by year.

In the individual files it is only present a description in a very concise manner, without images and detailed documentation on the restorations.

The database has many problems due to the lack of information on the data but it could be interesting due to the structure proposed by Archimista.

The founding law of the **Central Institute for Restoration** established that it was equipped with an Archive for the documentation of restorations, with the Fondazione CHANGES - Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society

task of collecting data relating to all restorations carried out by the Institute. As Cesare Brandi, founder and first director, clarified, the objective was to "hand down the precise memory of the procedures carried out and the measures adopted". The images and documents preserved in the Archive mainly concern works and artefacts belonging to public, private and ecclesiastical institutes, restored by the ICR. Technical and scientific consultancy interventions, exhibitions, conferences, conventions promoted by the ICR or in which the Institute actively participated are also documented. In particular, the Archive preserves approximately 4,000 x-rays, approximately 60,000 negatives of various formats, from 35 mm to 18x24 and as many prints, approximately 55,000 slides also of various formats, from 35 mm to 13x18. The most precious collection is that of the silver bromide gelatin glass plate negatives: approximately 11,000 plates produced by the internal photographic laboratory since the first years of the Institute's activity. They are mostly in the 18x24 format.

In the Archive there are also cards and photographs relating to stratigraphic sections carried out in the years between 1952 and 1976 and cards relating to microbiological and chemical investigations carried out between 1972 and 1982.

Inside the files there are often, in addition to photographic documentation, reports, restoration sheets, results of scientific investigations relating to works or artefacts.

Between 2008 and 2013, a project was carried out to reorganise, catalog and digitize all the images and documents preserved in the Archive, developed with the IT Section of the ICR, coordinated and directed by the Archive staff, and performed by the company Corvallis S.r.l. of Padua, winner of a public tender. This portal, called ARES, the result of this work, has been available on the Internet since 2014.

The database is not open access, the user must register on the portal.

Currently the cards are designed following ministerial directives and ICCD cards but the information visible without registration is scarce.

dati.cultura.gov.it is the platform where the Ministry of Culture (MiC) publishes its information assets according to the linked open data (LOD).

The first LODs published represent the result of a cooperation process between the central institutes and the general directorates of the MiC and connect their datasets from different sources: database of cultural places; records of Archives and Libraries; database of the Catalog of cultural heritage; other documentary and photographic databases.

All MiC datasets in open data and linked open data format are described on the Catalog page, based on the specifications of the Agency for Digital Italy (AGID).

The data.beniculturali.it project was born in 2014 with a strong experimental connotation and is aimed at enhancing the information assets of the MiC through linked open data, in line with the standards indicated by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).

The platform is the result of the first operational step of the project (2014-2016) and also a cooperation process between the central institutes and the general directorates of the MiC. In this first phase, the data of the Places of Culture, the records of the Archives and Libraries, and some data on the physical containers from the Catalog of Cultural Heritage were released in LOD. The data were also linked with other documentary and photographic databases and with external data from the linked data cloud.

The linked open data (LOD) model offers a unique opportunity to strengthen collaboration with local authorities and private individuals and increase the quantity and quality of information thanks to the possibility of automatically connecting MiC data to external "data" reservoirs. open", thus contributing to mutual enrichment.

The second step of the project (from November 2017) sees the ICCD make use of Linked Open Data as a vehicle for publishing the data of the General Catalog of Cultural Heritage, providing for the connection between the Places of Culture and the cultural heritage contained therein, with the hope that this platform can encourage better online enjoyment of our country's cultural heritage. The platform is essentially a machine-to-machine (m2m) interface that offers linked open data that can be queried directly from any application, thus responding to the needs of having standardized and interoperable data expressed by various communities of developers and users. Applications, user-friendly interfaces and useful services for citizens, students, researchers, tourists and other categories of users can be developed on this data.

In 2019, two new agreements were activated between the Central Institute for Cataloging and Documentation (ICCD) and the Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies (ISTC) of the CNR and with the University of Bologna.

Through them, the ICCD intends to complete the ArCo Project and start the ArCo4Science Project.

Actually on the online platform Catalog of Cultural Heritage there are open access sheets in PDF which contain few information on the restorations and qualitative judgments on the state of conservation (mediocre, good, fair).

SICaRweb (<http://sicar.beniculturali.it:8080/>)

SICaRweb is an online information system for the documentation, planning and management of restoration sites, which integrates the geometric representation of the property and the respective thematic maps, essential for the restoration, with the management of heterogeneous information organized in a data-base structured into dedicated tabs.

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Inside, all the data, which can be inserted and consulted online, can be connected, grouped and geo-referenced according to the needs of the individual artefact and restoration. The protagonists of the restoration intervention, in the most varied professions, can map and consult on the measurable representation of the property the areas of degradation and intervention and geo-reference all the accompanying technical and documentary information.

In this way SICaRweb guarantees a unitary view of the degraded surfaces, the interventions carried out and the associated information and allows you to perform precision calculations and statistics, offering valid decision-making support for the economic and temporal planning of the works and subsequent monitoring. Once the construction site is completed, all the collected documentation is already organised, archived and easily consultable thanks to the cross-research guaranteed by the system.

SICaRweb therefore responds to the following needs: use open source resources for work; consultation, from different workstations; provide a unified and structured view of the data; build the scientific final balance in progress; contribute to the construction of a searchable database to compare systems and working methods.

The database is online and not open access, the user must register to the site or use the guest access.

The database is made up of various items: interactive map, general data (immovable artworks, movable artworks, movements), projects, diagnostics, restorations, architectural archaeology, photographic documentation.

The sheets are made up from ICCD standard.

Palazzo Spinelli

Glossario delle tecniche artistiche e del restauro

(<https://www.palazzospinelli.org/argomed/find-argomed-ita.asp>)

This platform online from 2000 and open access is a Glossary of artistic and restoration techniques, not sheet on restorations but is significant for the structure of the platform.

Three types of search: lemma, the descriptive part, Keywords.

On the website of Palazzo Spinelli there is a section "Restoration" (<https://www.restauro.net/restauro/>), where there are some pages about past restorations by the Centre, divided by techniques.

For each restoration the state of conservation of the artworks and the type of intervention carried out are analytically reported.

On the website [Save Venice](https://www.savevenice.org/conservation-archives) (<https://www.savevenice.org/conservation-archives>) since 2017 there are PDF publications of the various restorations sponsored by Save Venice, digitized and open access.

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From 2023 on the website of Pinacoteca di Brera in Milan (<https://pinacotecabrera.org/collezioni/restauri/>) there is a section "Restorations" with intervention of collection's artworks.

In these sheets there are a description of the restoration and photographic documentation.

The C2RMF – Centre for Research and Restoration of the Museums of France (data.culture.gouv.fr)

The French Museums Research and Restoration Center (C2RMF) implements, in liaison with the curators responsible for the collections, the policy of the French Museums Service of the General Directorate of Heritage in terms of research, preventive conservation and restoration of the collections of French museums.

The archives and library department creates and maintains documentation on the materials, techniques and restoration of the works of public institutions described in the EROS (European research open system) database.

This dataset allows access to image records produced during the restoration or analysis of works coming to the Center.

Each work has a unique identifier (C2RMF reference number) which is found in all three datasets.

This data is offered under an Open License (Etalab), free of charge and in open formats which allow reuse, while respecting the legislation in force (respect for the various secrets and interests protected by law).

Bibliographic Database of the Conservation Information Network (<https://bcin.info/vufind/>)

Available online since 1987, BCIN is a trusted resource for professionals, museums and other heritage organizations. It facilitates retrieval and exchange of information on cultural heritage preservation.

For now, the database contains more than 260,000 citations, is open access and available from 2021 thanks to Emme.Bi.Soft S.r.l.

Find the most relevant books, articles and other bibliographic materials on conservation, preservation and restoration of cultural heritage.

Getty

<https://www.getty.edu/publications/conserving-canvas/glossary/>

This glossary is based on the Handbook of Terms Used in the Lining of Paintings, selected and curated by Westby Percival-Prescott and Gillian Lewis by the Conference on Comparative Lining Techniques, Greenwich, Londra, 1974, and edited in Lining Paintings: Papers from the Greenwich Conference on Comparative Technology of Rivestimento (Villers 2003b).

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DISCO: Data Integration for Conservation Science
(<https://www.archesproject.org/>)

Arches is an open source software platform freely available for cultural heritage organizations to independently deploy to help them manage their cultural heritage data.

The distribution of open source software is controlled by special, free licenses, most of which require that modifications be made available to the community. Arches is distributed under the GNU Affero General Public License, version 3 (AGPL3). The AGPL3 is a variation of the GNU General Public License, the most widely recognized free software license. It allows the Arches code to be copied and modified without restriction, and it stipulates that copies and modified versions of Arches must be distributed under the same license, without any additional restrictions. The AGPL3 is specially designed so that modifications to software used on network servers become available to the development community.

Nanorestart

<http://www.nanorestart.eu/>

This is a website open access where are offered some cases with a few descriptions of restorations conducted with the use of nanotechnologies. There are no precise cards but general descriptions of the works and the techniques used.

3. FAIR data

The management and dissemination of data produced within the project follow the FAIR principles, ensuring that research outputs are **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. These principles support the long-term scientific value of the datasets generated during the project and facilitate their reuse in future research, conservation planning, and educational activities.

The application of FAIR principles is particularly relevant in interdisciplinary research contexts such as cultural heritage studies, where historical documentation, environmental monitoring data, biological observations, and digital heritage outputs must coexist within a coherent framework. In the present research activities, FAIR data management enables the integration of datasets dedicated to restoration.

According to FAIR principles ensures, the information generated within the project remains accessible and useful beyond the duration of the research activities.

3.1 Making data findable

Ensuring that research data can be easily located and identified is a central objective of the data management strategy adopted in this project. The datasets generated through this research are documented through structured metadata that describe the context in which the data were produced.

The use of structured metadata for these different categories of data ensures that research outputs can be efficiently identified and retrieved by researchers and heritage professionals.

3.2 Making data accessible

Accessibility represents a key component of the dissemination strategy adopted within the project.

Digital technologies contribute significantly to improving accessibility. These digital tools are particularly useful for ensuring accessibility for individuals who may encounter physical barriers when visiting archaeological sites or historic buildings.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Interoperability is achieved through the adoption of standardized data formats and digital tools that allow datasets to be integrated and analyzed across different research domains.

Environmental monitoring data are stored in digital formats compatible with commonly used scientific software and data analysis platforms.

3.4 Increasing data reuse

The reuse of research data represents one of the most important objectives of the FAIR data framework. Within the present project, data reuse is encouraged through clear documentation of research methodologies and through the development of replicable educational activities.

4. Allocation of resources

The implementation of the research described in this deliverable requires the coordinated use of human, technical, and institutional resources distributed across the different research institutions involved in the CHANGES project.

The interdisciplinary nature of the project involves collaboration among researchers working in fields. The combination of these human, technical, and institutional resources enables the successful implementation of interdisciplinary research across the different heritage contexts considered in the project.

5. Data security

The security and long-term preservation of research data represent essential components of the data management strategy adopted within the project. The datasets generated during the research activities ensuring the integrity and safe storage of these datasets is necessary both for the continuity of the research and for the future reuse of the collected information.

Data generated during the project are stored using secure infrastructures provided by the participating universities and research institutions. These infrastructures typically include institutional cloud storage platforms, protected university servers, and locally managed storage systems maintained within the research laboratories. The use of institutional storage systems ensures that research data remain accessible to authorized researchers while being protected from accidental loss or unauthorized modification.

6. Ethics

Ethical considerations play a fundamental role in the research carried out within the project.

All research activities described in this deliverable are therefore developed in accordance with the conservation guidelines and regulatory frameworks established by the competent heritage authorities responsible for the management of the sites involved in the study.

Through these practices, the project promotes a responsible approach to cultural heritage research and contribute positively to the protection and long-term preservation of the historical environments under study.

Appendix – Databases or platforms mapped

Istitution	Description	Software	Analysis of examples in detail	Description of the type of technology used	From	Sponsored by	Online	Open Access
SISCA	Archive of restoration records relating to the heritage of the Sicilian Superintendency	https://wp.datatables.com/	Yes	Yes	n.d.	SISCA	Yes	Yes
Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Firenze	ongoing digitization of the Restoration and Photographic Fund with the open source software Archimista (previously used CDS-ISIS and SiCar software) PNRR Stream 5 "Digitization of restoration archives" MIC3 – Investment 1.1 "Digital strategies and platforms for cultural	Archimista	N.d.	n.d.	Ongoing	PNRR	n.d.	n.d.

	heritage" Sub- investment 1.1.5 – Digitization"							
ICR, Roma	Online restoration files (various sections: historical-critical analysis, techniques, state of conservation , previous intervention, restoration intervention, bibliography)	ICR website	Yes	Yes	n.d.	Istituto Centrale per il Restauro	Yes	Yes
ARES (ISCR Roma)	Photographic archive of restoration documentation	http://www.iscr-ares.beniculturali.it/ares/home.do	n.d.	n.d.	2014	ICR, Roma	Yes	No (registration required)
Istituto Centrale per la Patologia degli Archivi e del Libro	Information within the archive units is generally reported (documentation relating to the interventions carried out by the Central Institute for Book Pathology between 1953 and 2010). The Historical Restoration Archive	Archivista	No	no	Ongoing	Istituto Centrale per la Patologia degli Archivi e del Libro	Yes	Yes

	section is currently involved in the PNRR Stream 5 project "Digitization of Restoration Archives."							
Banca dati RES.I.	Archivio Storico Nazionale dei Restauratori Italiani		Yes	Yes	2022	Associazione Secco Suardo	Yes	Yes
ICCD, Roma	In the online files of the "Catalogue of Cultural Heritage" there is the string "Conservation" with a brief summary of the restoration interventions carried out and a qualitative assessment of the work (mediocre, fair, good)	ArCo	No	No	2021	ICCD, Roma	Yes	Yes
SICaWeb	http://sicar.beniculturali.it:8080/webseite/ricerca-in-sicar/	ArtPast Applicazione informatica in Rete per la Tutela e la valorizzazione del Patrimonio culturale nelle aree	Yes	Yes	2008	MiC	Yes	No

		Sottoutilizzate (http://www.artpast.it/ccd.beniculturali.it)						
Palazzo Spinelli	Glossary of artistic and restoration techniques	https://www.palazzospinelli.org/argomed/find-argomed-ita.asp	Yes	Yes	2000	Palazzo Spinelli	Yes	Yes
Save Venice	These are PDF publications of the various restorations on the Save Venice website, digitized and open access.	https://www.savevenice.org/conservation-archives	Yes	Yes	2017	Save Venice received a grant from the Gladys Kriebel Delmas Foundation	Yes	Yes
Pinacoteca di Brera	Section on the "Restorations" website with worksheets	https://pinacotecabrera.org/collezioni/restauri/	Yes	Yes	2023		Yes	Yes
C2RMF – Centre for Research and Restoration of the Museums of France	https://c2rmf.fr/nos-projets-0	data.culture.gouv.fr/la-plateforme-de-donnees-ouvertes-du-ministere-de-la-culture	Yes	Yes	2002	French Ministry of Culture	Yes	Yes
Bibliographic Database of the Conservation Information Network	Find the most relevant books, articles and other bibliographic	https://bcin.info/vufind/	No	No	2021	Emme.Bi.Soft S.r.l.	Yes	No

	materials on conservation , preservation and restoration of cultural heritage							
Getty	https://www.getty.edu/publications/conserving-canvas/glossary/		No	Yes	2004	Getty Trust 2004	Yes	Yes
Getty Conservation Institute	DISCO: Data Integration for Conservation Science (https://www.archesproject.org/)	Archeo	No	No	n.d.	Getty Foundation	Yes	no
Nanorestart	This is a website offering examples of restorations conducted using nanotechnology. There are no specific descriptions, but general descriptions of the works and techniques used. http://www.nanorestart.eu/		Yes	Yes	2015	funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020	Yes	Yes

Partner	Type of storage	Backup policies
Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	MS OneDrive, Uni laptops	OneDrive file recovery function
Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa	Google Drive, Uni laptops	Google Drive restoring of deleted files
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Not known	Not known
DTC Lazio	Not known	Not known
Engineering	Not known	Not known
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	Not known	Not known
Università degli Studi di Ferrara	Google Drive, Unilaptops, external hard-disk	Google Drive
Università degli Studi di Firenze	Not known	Not known
Università degli Studi di Parma	Not known	Not known
Università degli Studi di Torino	Google Drive, laptops owned by the University	Google Drive, laptops owned by the University

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